

THE MORPHOLOGY OF IN SITU COMPOSITES OF MODIFIED PPO / LCP AND PES / LCP

Guo Meili, Zhang Peng, Wang Yin, Wang Zhi and Gao Yongdan
Department of Materials Science and Engineering
Beijing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics
Beijing, 100083, China

ABSTRACT

Two non-liquid crystalline polymers, PES and MPPO were melt blended with a thermotropic liquid crystalline copolyester, PET / PHB 60mol%, by extrusion and injection molding to form in situ composites. Morphology study by SEM showed that the fiber forming ability of LCP, which is most important for LCP to play a role of reinforcement, strongly depended on the viscosity ratio of matrix to LCP and the extensional flow of the melt experienced during processing.

INTRODUCTION

In situ composites produced by blending thermotropic LCPs with common non-liquid crystalline plastics have riveted great attention and considered as being a generation of super engineering plastics because of their better processability than and comparable mechanical properties with short glass fiber reinforced plastics. Papers on this subject are piled up. Among them there is no lack of successful examples and some of them have been patented[1-3]. However, many blended systems have not reached the desired properties yet, indicating that there is still a long way to go to accumulate a weath of experience universally suitable for preparing in situ composites with good quality.

The most important factor that determines the reinforcing effect of LCPs in an in situ composite may be the fiber forming ability of LCP during processing. This work was to study the influence of processing techniques and the viscosity ratio of non-LCP matrix to LCP on the fiber forming ability of LCP through morphology observation.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Materials

A thermotropic liquid crystalline polymer, poly (terephthalate-co-hydroxybenzoic acid), PET / PHB 60mol%, and two non-LCPs, a modified polyphenylene oxide(MPPO) and polyethersulfone(PES) were chosen for preparing in situ composites. Some of their physical properties are shown in Table 1. The weight fractions of LCP were 2, 5,10 and 20% in MPPO / LCP and 5,10 and 20% in PES / LCP, respectively.

Table 1 some of the physical properties of raw materials

property	LCP	MPPO	PES
intrinsic viscosity, $[\eta](\text{dl} / \text{g})$, at 25°C in a mixed solvent of phenol / tetrachloroethane	1.0	—	—
density at room temperature(g / cm^3)	1.3	1.07	—
melt index($\text{g} / 10\text{min}$)	5.3(250°C)	5.3(260°C)	0.53(310°C)

2. Processing

Blending were carried out with a single screw extruder. The barrel temperatures of the front segment, i.e., the metering zone, were 250°C for MPPO / LCP and 310 °C for PES / LCP, respectively. The extruded strands were further drawn into thin ones followed by quenching in cold water. The draw ratio, which was defined as the ratio of the cross-section areas of a strand before(S0) and after(SI) drawing, varied in the range of 2-40.

Bar specimens were injection molded with a single screw injection molding machine, SZ-60A. The barrel temperatures of the front segment were the same as those for extrusion and the mould temperatures were up to 80°C for MPPO / LCP and up to 120°C for PES / LCP, respectively.

3. Morphology observation

The morphology characteristics of in situ composites were studied in the following two ways: (1) Fracture surface investigation: Thin extruded and drawn strands or injection molded bars were broken in liquid nitrogen and fracture surfaces were investigated with a SEM, Hitachi S- 530, after being sputter coated with copper; (2) Solvent etched residue observation: Small pieces of samples were cut from thin strands or different parts of an injection moulded bar. Each sample was immersed in tetrachloroethane for about 24 hours to allow the matrix in it to dissolve in the solvent. Then the undissolved residue

was dredged up slowly and carefully onto a small copper mesh disc for SEM study after the solvent in it being evaporated and its surface coated with copper.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Extruded and Drawn Strands

Fig.1 and Fig.2 show the typical morphology of the fracture surfaces of extruded and drawn strands of MPPO / LCP and PES / LCP, respectively. Bamboo shoots like fibrils with a diameter of approximately a couple of microns could be seen from all fracture surfaces, even when the LCP content in a strand was as low as 2%.

SEM observation of the solvent etched strands further revealed the highly oriented fibrils aligning along the drawing direction as shown in Fig. 3, indicating that the LCP had a good fiber forming ability during this processing. However, it was found that the size and distribution of fibrils was influenced by the blend composition and processing conditions. Briefly, the following aspects may be summarized.

(1) The fiber forming ability of LCP in PES matrix, was better than in MPPO. As can be seen from Fig.1 and Fig.2, the fibrils existing in PES / LCP appear thinner and longer than those in MPPO / LCP. Melt index testing showed that the viscosity ratio of PES to LCP at 310°C, which was the barrel temperature at which PES / LCP was blended, was far greater than that of MPPO to LCP at 250°C, which was the barrel temperature at which MPPO / LCP was blended[4-5].

(2) With increasing LCP content, the fibrils became thicker, their size distribution wider and their location distribution less uniform. In addition, the skin-core structure could not be found until the LCP fraction approached to 20%. In a skin more fibrils were there than in a core. In the case of PES(80) / LCP(20), many thin sheet like LCP in stead of fibrils formed at the surface of a strand, which may be attributed to either the limited miscibility of PES and LCP or the limited blending efficiency of the single screw extruder employed in this work.

(3) The larger the draw ratio, the thinner the fibrils in the strands and the larger their aspect ratios, therefore the higher the reinforcing effect of the LCP, as can be seen from the increase in the strength of strands with the increasing draw ratio(Fig.4)

2. Injection moulded bars

All the fracture surfaces of injection moulded bars showed a typical skin-core structure, with a high content of LCP in the form of fibrils or sheet like foils in the skin and a relatively low content of LCP in the form of spheric or ellipsoidal droplets / particles in the

Fig.1 SEM graphs of extruded and drawn strands of MPPO / LCP with a LCP fraction of (a)2%,(b)5%,(c)10% and(d) 20%, respectively.

Fig.2 SEM graphs of extruded and drawn strands of PES / LCP with a LCP fraction of (a)5%, (b)10% and (c)20%, respectively.

Fig.3 Morphology of (a) MPPO / LCP and (b) PES / LCP strands after their being etched with tetrachloroethane for 24 hours.

core as shown in Fig.5. Compared with the morphology of thin drawn strands described above, it appeared that the fiber forming ability of LCP was much poorer in injection molding. As a matter of fact, even in the skin of an injection moulded bar, the orientation of fibrils was not as good as that in a strand, and the aspect ratios seemed much smaller (see Fig.6). Mechanical testing results also showed that the reinforcing action of LCP in the injection molded bars was not as effective as in the strands: With increasing LCP content, the increase in tensile modulus or strength of bars was not as significant as expected [5].

Those differences in morphology and mechanical properties between thin strands and relatively thick injection moulded bars of same composition may be attributed to the following factors: (1) The difference in the extent of extensional flow of the melt experienced in the two processing techniques: In extrusion and drawing, extensional flow predominates while in injection molding, shear flow may dominate over extensional flow, depending on the mould geometry and processing conditions. It is known that extensional flow is more important for LCP to form fibrils than shear flow; (2) The difference in the periods for LCP fibrils which had formed to relax before they were frozen in: in thick injection moulded bars the relaxation periods are longer than those in extruded and drawn strands, particularly for the material away from the mould cavity wall.

The morphology differences between different parts of an injection moulded bar are apparently related to the shear rate distribution during mould filling, with the maximum value at a short distance from the cavity wall and a minimum value in the core, and the different relaxation periods, which are increased with the increasing depth.

Cross polarized optical microscopy observation showed that LCP fibrils could rapidly change into droplets when heated to a temperature above its melting point. According to V.G.Kulichikhin etc. [6], it only takes a time less than one minute.

It has been known that the fiber forming ability of LCP in injection molding increased with the increase in injection pressure and with the decrease in barrel temperature and mould temperature as well. However, for each specific non-LCP / LCP system, it seems there is only a narrow processing window suitable for producing injection moldings in which LCP plays a role of effective reinforcement and sometimes a specific third component as a coupling agent need incorporating, which is not universally applicable as a silicane coupling agent for glass fibers. On the contrary, the quality of injection molded bars of short glass fiber reinforced PES or MPPO was easier to be ensured than their in situ composite counterparts, though their flow ability was relatively poor.

Therefore, a question is naturally raised: When in situ composite articles having complex shapes are to be produced by injection molding technique, is it possible to take some measures universally applicable to properly and uniformly control the extensional flow and the relaxation periods to ensure the LCP in it to fully realize its reinforcing effect?

Fig.4 Strength and draw ratio relationships of extruded and drawn strands of MPPO / LCP

Fig.5 SEM graphs of different parts of an injection moulded bar of MPPO(80) / LCP(20), showing the morphology of (a) the outer skin (b) the inner skin and (c) the core.

Fig.6 Morphology of the solvent etched skin of an injection moulded bar of MPPO(80) / LCP(20)

CONCLUSIONS

The LCP, PET / PHB 60mol%, has a good fiber forming ability when blended with PES and MPPO by extrusion followed by drawing, hence exhibiting a good reinforcing effect in the in situ composites. It is attributed to the high viscosity ratios of both the matrices to the LCP, the predominant extensional flow the melts experienced and the short relaxation time for LCP fibrils to relax before they were frozen in during this processing. However, It is not easy for LCP to realize its reinforcement in injection moldings.

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